

PERCEPTION OF PATIENTS TOWARDS OPEN, LAPAROSCOPIC, AND ROBOTIC SURGERY IN GENERAL SURGICAL PROCEDURES AT JINNAH POSTGRADUATE MEDICAL CENTRE KARACHI.

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Abstract

Background:

Laparoscopic and robotic procedures are surgical innovations that have revolutionized the provision of operative care because they provide minimally invasive sources of treatment. Nevertheless, patient awareness and perception of these strategies are not well known in resource limited countries like Pakistan.

Objective:

The objectives of our research was to evaluate patient perception about open, laparoscopic, and robotic surgeries, factors that affect their decisions in choosing these surgical procedures, and the level of awareness and misperceptions of these surgical methods in the tertiary care hospital, Jinnah postgraduate medical Centre (JPMC) at Karachi.

Methods:

A cross-sectional survey was conducted at Jinnah Post Graduate Medical Centre Karachi between January and October 2025. Adult patients who underwent or were about to undergo general surgery were recruited using a structured questionnaire that measured demographics, surgical history, source of information, awareness and preferences on surgical approaches. The analysis of data was carried out with SPSS 25 software. The Chi-square and Fisher Exact tests were used to evaluate the association with statistical significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Results:

966 patients were included in study. Healthcare professionals (70.8%), friends and family (24.1%), and internet (5.1%) were the main sources of surgical

information. The open surgery was seen as the least expensive, but laparoscopic surgery was viewed as the most preferred due to its quick recovery and less painful postoperative period. This was identified to be a limitation in awareness of robotic surgery with 48.7% of patients having no knowledge of how robotic surgery is performed and 58.8% having the perception that it is the costliest of all surgical modalities.

Conclusion:

The study reveals significant differences in the perceptions and awareness of patients regarding open, laparoscopic, and robotic surgeries in a low-resource hospital. The lack of knowledge about robotic surgery and financial issues also play a major role in patient preferences. Increased patient education and improved communication between surgeons and patients can potentially help increase informed decision-making and uptake of minimally invasive surgical procedures.

INTRODUCTION:

The combination of clinical medicine and technological improvements has transformed surgery, shifting the paradigm of traditional open surgery to the new direction of minimally invasive surgical (MIS) surgery.¹ These new technologies, specifically laparoscopic and robotic surgery offer significant benefits, including shorter hospital stays, faster recovery, reduced perioperative complications, and improved cosmetic outcomes.^{2,3} Robotic surgery has experienced substantial growth, with utilization increasing nearly 400-fold between 2000 to 2010, highlighting its expanding role in modern surgical care⁴. In comparison with conventional laparoscopy, robotic surgery provides higher depth perception, three-dimensional imaging, tremor elimination, and greater instrument dexterity, potentially making the operation more precise.⁵ In spite of all these technological leaps, patient knowledge and attitudes toward various surgical modalities remain limited, especially in low-resource health systems like Pakistan.⁶ Patient perceptions play a critical role in surgical decision-making and significantly influence treatment satisfaction, adherence, and overall surgical outcome.^{7,9} In developed nations, studies in gynecology and urology have explored patient acceptance of robotic surgery, revealing varied awareness and concerns related to cost, safety and access to technology.¹⁰ However, evidence regarding patient perception of open, laparoscopic, and robotic surgery within general

surgery remain limited, particularly in low resource settings.

Health sector in Pakistan faces certain problems of the lack of financial resources, the deficiency of the access to the patient to the advanced surgical technology and lack of the formal patient education programs. In other low-and-middle-income countries (LMICs), the previous studies have demonstrated that the decisions made by patients are usually informed by factors related to costs, surgeon referral, and availability of robotic equipment^{11,12}. In Ghana, as an illustration, a study by Gyedu et al., found that the cost and preference of the surgeon were primary contributors to surgical decision-making in resource-constrained settings¹³. Similarly, Irani et al. also reported that the advantages of robotic surgery were recognized by the patients in India but affordability, and access were major challenges to its widespread use¹⁴. These findings suggest that there is an urgent need to explore the perception of patients in Pakistan, where the parallel healthcare limitations are dominant.

The research will fill this knowledge gap by evaluating the perceptions of patients regarding open, laparoscopic, and robotic surgery in a tertiary care unit in Pakistan. The assessment of patient knowledge, misperceptions, and drivers of surgical preference will help the area to improve their patient education, shared decision-making, and optimize the provision of surgical services as a part of the contribution that this study will make. Lastly, patient awareness and surgical innovation

must be congruent to endorse informed decision-making and patient-centered care as a key priority in modern surgical practice.

Methods:

The cross-sectional study was conducted in the Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre (JPMC), a Karachi-based tertiary care hospital in Pakistan, between march to December 2024. The Institutional Review Board of JPMC (IRB No: NO.F.2-81/2024-GENL/236/JPMC) approved the ethical approval. For participants aged 14-17 years, written informed consent was obtained from parents or legal guardians in accordance with institutional ethical guidelines. Recruitment of patients was done using predetermined inclusion criteria: age ≥ 14 years planned or currently undergoing general surgery, and ability to give informed assent or consent. Patients with cognitive impairment affecting response reliability and those unwilling to participate were excluded. A structured validated questionnaire was developed, including demographic information, surgical history, and awareness, perception, knowledge, and attitudes related sections on open,

laparoscopic, and robotic surgery. The questionnaire was pilot tested and reviewed by experienced surgeons to ensure content validity. The questionnaire primarily consisted of closed-ended questions to ensure standardized responses. Data were collected from surgical inpatient wards and outpatient departments. Involvement was on a voluntary basis. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. The Chi-square test and Fisher's exact test were applied to assess associations between variables.

Results:

966 patients were involved in the study. The age ranged from 41.49 ± 11.93 years, of which 47.9% were between 14 and 40 years, and 52.1% were more than 40 years. Female patients (57.3%) were more than males (42.7%). Most (40.0%) of them had a history of previous surgery. Educational history was not uniform and comprised 22.1% without education, 38.8% less than high school level, and 13.8% having college or more. Socioeconomic status comprised 50.0% from the lower class, 33.4% from the middle class, and 16.6% from the upper class.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

Variables	Mean \pm SD	95% C. I
Age in years	41.49 \pm 11.93	40.74-42.25
Age Group		
14 - 40 Years	463 (47.9%)	
>40 Years	503 (52.1%)	
Gender		
Male	412 (42.7%)	
Female	554 (57.3%)	
History of Previous Surgery		
Yes	386 (40.0%)	
No	580 (60.0%)	
Educational Status		
Uneducated	214 (22.1%)	
Less than Higher School	375 (38.8%)	
High School	244 (25.3%)	

College	109 (11.3%)
Graduate	24 (2.5%)
Surgeries Performed Previously	
2C Sections	13 (1.3%)
3C-sections	14 (1.4%)
4C -sections fibroidectomy	14 (1.4%)
Appendectomy	10 (1.0%)
Breast Surgery	13 (1.3%)
C-Section	70 (7.2%)
C-Section + Appendeiha	10 (1.0%)
Caesar	10 (1.0%)
Cholecystectomy	26 (2.7%)
Ex-Lap	13 (1.3%)
Eye Surgery	10 (1.0%)
Hysterectomy/Liver mass (hepatotomy)	14 (1.4%)
Laparoscopic	13 (1.3%)
Ortho after RTA	10 (1.0%)
Thyroidectomy	13 (1.3%)
Socioeconomic Status	
Lower Class	483(50.0%)
Middle Class	323(33.4%)
Upper Class	160(16.6%)

The majority of the participants received surgical information from physicians (70.8%), then family/friends (24.1%) and the internet (5.1%).

When queried regarding the best surgical method, 30.1% chose open surgery, 31.9% laparoscopic surgery, and 34.8% robotic surgery (Table 1).

Table 2: Awareness, Perception, and Knowledge of Surgical Approaches

Variable	n (%)
Source of Surgical Information	
Doctor	684 (70.8%)
Family/Friends	233 (24.1%)
Internet	49 (5.1%)
Preferred Surgical Approach	
Open Abdominal	291 (30.1%)
Laparoscopic	308 (31.9%)
Robotic	336 (34.8%)
All are the same	31 (3.2%)
Perception of Surgery Costs	
Open Abdominal	244 (25.3%)

Laparoscopic	154 (15.9%)
Robotic	568 (58.8%)

Over half of the respondents (58.8%) viewed robotic surgery as the costliest. Thirty-five percent (35.1%) linked robotic surgery with needing more

technical skills, while 42.8% thought that open surgery needed more expertise (Table 2).

Table 3: Attitude Toward Different Surgical Approaches

Variable	n (%)
Technical Skill Requirement	
Open Abdominal	413 (42.8%)
Laparoscopic	47 (4.9%)
Robotic	339 (35.1%)
Upon Surgeon's Decision	167 (17.3%)
Understanding of Robotic Surgery	
Surgeon controls robotic arms	151 (15.6%)
Surgeon instructs robot to perform while supervising	345 (35.7%)
Don't know	470 (48.7%)

In terms of understanding various surgical modalities, the younger group (14-40 years) showed improved awareness, with 24.5% showing a moderate level of understanding and 7.2% having a clear distinction between open,

laparoscopic, and robotic surgery. A high percentage of females (45.8%) said they did not know the differences compared to 34.0% males (Table 3).

Table 4: Patient knowledge of open, laparoscopic, and robotic abdominal surgeries

	Understand the difference among robotic, open, and laparoscopic abdominal surgery	Moderate Understanding	Did not Understand how Different Surgeries Works
Age Group			
14 - 40 Years	114 (24.6)	33 (7.1)	184 (39.7)
>40 Years	42 (8.3)	33 (6.6)	210 (41.7)
Gender			
Male	97 (23.5)	20 (4.9)	140 (34.0)
Female	59 (10.6)	46 (8.3)	254 (45.8)
Educational Status			
Uneducated	0 (0.0)	13 (6.1)	148 (69.2)
Less than Higher School	78 (20.8)	13 (3.5)	174 (46.4)
High School	64 (26.2)	20 (8.2)	46 (18.9)
College	14 (12.8)	20 (18.3)	26 (23.9)
History in in of Previous Surgery			
Yes	49 (12.7)	43 (11.1)	157 (40.7)
No	107 (18.4)	23 (4.0)	237 (40.9)
Socioeconomic Status			

Lower Class	77 (15.9)	36 (7.5)	203 (42.0)
Middle Class	50 (15.5)	18 (5.6)	130 (40.2)
Upper Class	29 (18.1)	12(7.5)	61 (38.1)

Values represent in row as percentages, the age group, gender, educational status, and previous surgery were statistically significantly correlated ($p < 0.001$), whereas socioeconomic status did not show significant correlation with the level of knowledge ($p = 0.776$).

Table 4 shows that educational background also significantly contributed to the level of knowledge, with 69.2% of participants who were uneducated being unable to recognize surgical differences, whereas 18.2% of college-educated respondents were able to identify between them.

Table 5: Comparison of Patient Perceptions in Similar Studies

Study	Sample Size	Region	Preference for Open Surgery	Preference for Laparoscopic Surgery	Preference for Robotic Surgery	Key Findings
Our Study (2025)	966	Karachi, Pakistan	30.1%	31.9%	34.8%	Cost concerns favor open surgery; robotic perceived as most expensive
Irani et al. (2021)	850	India	40.2%	28.6%	25.1%	Higher open surgery preference due to trust in traditional methods
Gyedu et al. (2019)	600	Ghana	50.8%	29.4%	19.8%	Limited awareness of robotic surgery, cost barriers
Kim et al. (2020)	1,200	South Korea	10.4%	40.5%	45.6%	Higher robotic surgery preference in developed countries
Smith et al. (2022)	900	USA	8.7%	34.9%	55.2%	Strong inclination toward robotic surgery due to trust in technology

Table 5 showing comparison of different studies with our study. Regional variations exist in patient preferences for surgical modalities based on socioeconomic factors, accessibility of healthcare, and technological awareness.

In our study that was conducted in Karachi, 30.1% chose open surgery, 31.9% chose laparoscopic surgery, and 34.8% chose robotic surgery. This result aligned with the works of the Indian and Ghanaian studies, where open surgery was a preferable choice due to the hold on the traditional practice and the financial constraint. Nonetheless, research in South Korea and the USA showed more preference towards robotic surgery. Cost remains a significant factor in low resource economies like Pakistan and must be

touched upon through educational programs supporting the growth of awareness and acceptance of new methods of surgery. In general, the results point out the areas of patient awareness, their preference to surgery methods, and their familiarity with robotic-assisted methods. Educational background and the socioeconomic status played a significant role in influencing understanding and perceptions.

Discussion:

The study identifies significant knowledge gaps in the science of the surgical procedures, in particular robotic surgery. Patient knowledge was also influenced by differences in education, where the less educated patients were unable to differentiate between surgeries. There was statistically significant differentiation with college-educated patients having a better understanding of surgical options ($p < 0.0001$). The findings indicate the necessity of providing better patient education since 68.8% of patients who were not educated did not understand the principles of various surgeries. The absence of patient education regarding open, laparoscopic and robotic abdominal surgery remained despite 40.5% of the patients having a history of prior surgery^{15, 16}.

A study at Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, discovered that 70.7% ($n = 215$) of the patients had never heard about robotic surgery, which means that patients who present themselves at surgical specialty clinics have a severe deficit of knowledge and understanding of robotic-assisted surgery (RAS). The majority of the information regarding RAS was provided by the media instead of medical professionals.¹⁵

Irani et al. stated that the strongest predictors of better patient awareness between open, laparoscopic and robot-assisted surgeries included higher educational level and prior abdominal surgery. They highlighted that age and race did not have any significant impact on surgical knowledge and indicated that demographic factors do not solely determine patient comprehension¹⁶. Our findings support this because most patients depended on Health care professionals to gain information (70.9%), whereas friends/family (23.9%), and internet (5.2%). In a recent literature, the fast growth and expanding use of robotic surgery across the globe has been noted focusing on its potential and the challenges associated with the use of robotic surgery^{17, 18}. A study was conducted in Singapore, with misconceptions affecting the preferences towards robotic surgery, and the most common ones were beliefs that a robot is an independent being (43.6%), misconception that robot would perform incorrect procedures (55.1%), and misconception that robot cannot adapt to new conditions as a

human surgeon (55.1%). Only a very low percentage of patients thought robotic surgery was safer (29.2%), less painful (14.0%), or able to achieve better outcomes (29.0%). In accordance with the Ghana experience, laparoscopic surgeries were favored due to the speed of recovery, less pain, and improved cosmetic appearance, whereas open surgeries were also prevalent because of their affordability²⁰.

In Pakistan Robotic surgery has been mentioned as a newer but a constrained choice because of the high cost and limited availability, especially in government hospitals²¹. Worldwide, technological development and surgeon training programs are leading to the growing use of robotic surgery in common surgeries, particularly in high-income countries^{22, 23}.

However, the main obstacles in Pakistan are cost of installation and maintenance, untrained staff and institutional support. Such financial and logistical limitations deter the formation of robots programs in hospitals. The implementation would need high levels of investments on infrastructure development, training and awareness campaigns in order to be sustainable²⁴. Surveys of the perceptions of robotic-assisted surgery have been carried out in both surgical and patient groups, with ambivalent findings, with the safety, cost, and effectiveness concerns being factors that lead to the reluctance to adopt the technology²⁵.

There is clinical evidence that clinical benefits of robotic surgery are technologically advantageous, but patient perception is still influenced by less than ideal knowledge levels, which requires enhanced education^{26,27}. Other procedures where laparoscopic surgery has been reported preferred by patients include cholecystectomy and pancreatic surgery, primarily because of its minimally invasive nature, early recovery, and cosmetic advantages^{28,29}.

A significant proportion of participants in our study (49.1%) had limited or no knowledge of robotic surgery. Such misconceptions as the belief that robotic surgery is completely automated also underscore the importance of enhancing patient education and perioperative counseling.¹⁹

In our results, we found that patients thought that 35.3% believe the robot is told how to work by the

surgeon and then the robot performs the operation under the supervision of the surgeon^{19, 25}. This is the reason why clear communication is important to the patient so that they can make informed decisions. It is also highlighted in the literature that extensive perioperative counseling is a significant factor in the perception and experience of patients regarding robotic-assisted surgery.^{26, 27} As far as we can confirm, we do not have much data on patient perceptions of open, laparoscopic, and robotic surgery in the local setting. This underscores the significance of our research to give an understanding of the current patient knowledge.

This study, however, has limitations such as the possibility of having bias because of convenience sampling in a hospital, which does not reflect on the general population. Also, the respondents who had previously experienced robotic or laparoscopic surgery were not analyzed specifically and might affect the level of knowledge. Regardless of these constraints, our results formulate valuable information regarding the gaps in knowledge that might be even more substantial in communities with the lack of health education.

CONCLUSION:

This research study reveals a major knowledge gap in patients about surgical procedures, especially laparoscopic and robotic surgery. These knowledge gaps affect the knowledge about minimally invasive procedures, decision-making, and acceptance of these procedures among the patients. Education of patients' needs to be improved to tackle the misconceptions and encourage informed decisions. The media, policymakers, and healthcare providers must collaborate to promote social awareness and make sure that a patient is provided with correct and trustworthy information on the existing surgical procedures.

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